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Health Risk Assessment of Heavy Metal Contamination in Groundwater Near Industrial Zones in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Maintaining human health depends on having access to clean, drinkable water. Chronic exposure to heavy metals in drinking water can lead to a 30% increase in the incidence of cancer in industrial areas compared to non-industrial areas. Savar is one of the rapidly industrializing areas near Dhaka, home to a large portion of the ready-made garment industry. This research investigates heavy metal contamination in groundwater near the industrial area of Savar. The concentrations of heavy metals were measured using a variety of analytical techniques, including the dual-range arsenic test strip method, the Ferro Ver method, and atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS). Analysis revealed that the iron levels of one sample exceeded the standard value. The Hazard Quotient (HQ), Hazardous Index (HI), and carcinogenic risks (CR) revealed significant health exposure to arsenic and nickel in the research area. HQ value for Arsenic was 0.92 for adults and 1.94 for children, while the CR exceeded the limit. The HI 2.116 for children exceeding the risk levels. Arsenic has been demonstrated to cause hepatotoxicity, liver damage, associated with nephrotoxicity, immune system disorders. Nickel exposure effects like epigenetic changes and DNA damage. Notably, HI value for children is almost twice that of adults.

Keywords: Groundwater; heavy metal contamination, industrial area, drinking water; human health risk

Highlights

- Access to safe and potable water is crucial for maintaining human health, especially in rapidly industrializing areas like Savar near Dhaka.
- This study investigated the ingestion of heavy metals in groundwater near industrial zones using methods like dual-range arsenic test strips, Ferro Ver, and atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS).
- Our findings revealed that the iron concentration in groundwater samples

significantly exceeded the standard limits.

- Health risk assessments showed that the HQ value for As, the CR values for As and Ni, and the HI values for six metals surpassed the acceptable safety thresholds.
- The HI value for children was nearly double that of adults, indicating a greater vulnerability among the younger population.

Graphical Abstract

INTRODUCTION

In Bangladesh, 80% to 95% of residents rely on groundwater for drinking as well as domestic use[36]. Groundwater is one of the vital resources that is essential to people's existence, means of subsistence, and the economic development of a nation like Bangladesh[8,9]. About 90% of Bangladeshi people are directly dependent on a tube well as the primary safe source of

drinking water [11]. One of the world's major sources of freshwater is groundwater, which is kept in aquifers [21]. Water scarcity is one of the biggest challenges of the 21st century. Approximately 4 billion people and half of the world's irrigated agriculture currently live in areas where water scarcity occurs for at least one month out of the year [33]. Approximately one-third of the global population is anticipated

to utilize groundwater for various purposes, including domestic consumption and industrial applications. Ten countries in the Asia Pacific region have been ranked among the top countries regarding groundwater extraction.

The position of Bangladesh is 7th among the countries [3]. According to the Global Water Development Report 2024, China, India, the United States, Pakistan, Iran, and Mexico are the six countries that extract more water than Bangladesh [40]. With the objective to cope with worldwide issues, including better sanitation, equal access, and water quality, this goal is to "ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all" by 2030. For the sake of rising demand, groundwater has grown significantly over time, leading to inappropriate exploitation and a freshwater stress situation [25].

In the past few decades, urbanization and industrialization are two of the most widespread environmental changes in China, and the contamination of heavy metals and organic chemicals in groundwater often occurs in rapidly urbanized and industrialized areas [27]. Due to rapid urbanization and industrialization, not only is the environment polluted by excessive heavy metal deposits, but also various factories have been established in Bangladesh, especially in Savar Upazila of Dhaka district. Various types of untreated wastewater are discharged by these factories or industries, which contaminate the groundwater. When industrial effluents are released, these contaminants seep into the surface and groundwater and are gradually contaminated [18].

In industrial regions, heavy metals originate from a number of sources. Inappropriate disposal of waste, industrial runoff, and other pollution methods allow heavy metals to get into the groundwaters. 80% of

diseases in developing nations are brought on by water contamination [17]. The majority of Bangladesh's water-polluted regions are found in the country's most industrialized areas [19]. Identifying heavy metals is of primary importance in managing water resources because they influence the quality of groundwater and, consequently, human beings [4].

The objectives of the research are to determine the groundwater quality in the context of heavy metals in the research area and compare it with Bangladesh's standard of drinking water limits (BECR-2023) and WHO guidelines. In addition, the level of heavy metal pollution in groundwater and the health risk assessment due to heavy metals in the research region are examined. Health risks due to heavy metals were evaluated from different parts of the world, including Bangladesh, but there were few or no reports regarding both adults and children in terms of these six heavy metals.

Ingesting contaminated food, drinking polluted water, coming into contact with contaminated skin, and breathing in contaminated air are the four main ways that the human body is exposed to heavy metal ions [22,23]. Although several heavy metals, such as iron, copper, and zinc, are essential micronutrients, at higher concentrations they can be harmful to living beings [2,5]. Even at ppb (parts per billion) levels, the heavy metals are extremely toxic, poisonous, and pose a health risk [13,14].

These metals are detrimental to human health, causing damage to organs like the liver, kidneys, and nervous system, developmental problems in children, and immune system disorders [1]. Besides this, it may increase the risk of developing various types of cancer, respiratory problems, neurological effects, etc [16]. Estimated contaminant concentrations are typically compared with suggested

guideline levels in order to determine the danger to human health.

This method, by itself, however, is inadequate since it fails to identify the most important pollutants linked to prolonged exposure or to completely capture the levels of hazard. Therefore, a more thorough risk assessment is necessary for making well-informed decisions and setting priorities for remediation work[39]. Human health risk of a specific hazardous substance, even if below the recommended value, is dependent on the type of element, the level of the component to which the person is exposed, the period they are exposed, as well as how much they eat [12]. The outcomes of these evaluations will help guide remediation initiatives and policy choices, protecting local communities and enhancing water safety.

METHODS

Study Area

Savar Upazila was selected as the study area (Figures 1 and 2), which covers around 280.12 km² with a population of about 1.44 million. Savar Upazila is located at a latitude of 23.8583° North and a longitude of 90.2667° East. About 66,956 families live here. It is bounded by Kaliakair Upazila and Gazipur City Corporation in the north and Keraniganj Upazila in the south. Mirpur, Mohammadpur, Pallabi Thana, Uttara Thana in the East, Dhamrai Upazila, and Singair Upazila in the West.

The southern part of the Savar is formed by the sediments of the Banshai and Dhaleswari rivers. The major rivers here are Bansai, Turag, and Dhaleswari. There are also two more rivers, namely the Bridiganga and Ghazikhali. The rivers are getting seriously polluted due to the effluents of various industries and tanneries, and their existence is constantly threatened due to encroachment.

Agriculture and manufacturing are the two major economic sectors in Savar. Manufacturing facilities include the Ceramic industry, beverage industry, press and publication, garments industry, etc. Bangladesh Export Processing Zone is located in this Upazila. Besides this, Jalalabad Steel Limited and Padma Cans and Closures Factory Limited were situated in this region, which were related to heavy metal products. Metal producing factory, different industries, and some crucial locations were strategically selected for sampling, from which we collect drinking water.

The study area is shown in Figures 1 and 2, and Figure 2 was completed using the Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) interpolation method in QGIS 3.38. Consequently, the changing pattern of heavy metal concentration results of groundwater is presented in Figure 3 using the Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) interpolation method in ArcGIS 10.3.

*Fig. 1: Study Area (Savar Upazila)
(Source: Google)*

Fig. 2: Location-wise map of Savar Upazila using the IDW interpolation method in QGIS 3.38.

Sample Collection

In this study, samples were collected from 12 unions of Savar Upazila, which is adjacent to the metal and can-producing industry, various factories, etc., during November 2022. Three samples were collected from each union, after obtaining permission from the appropriate authority, and the sources were tubewells (36 samples in total). The sampling stations were selected in such a way that they not only represent an important place for metal but also the entire area of Savar Upazila. All the samples were collected from the submersible deep tubewell of residential

houses, and the others from local places and mosques. For sampling purposes, acidified plastic bottles of 500 ml capacity were used. We thoroughly washed and rinsed all the sampling containers with groundwater for analysis before sampling. Moreover, duplicate sampling was taken to ensure quality control, improve data reliability, and lower uncertainty. Since it is a standard best practice for environmental and groundwater studies.

Sample Analysis and Laboratory Testing

This study assessed groundwater quality and health risks in Savar Upazila, Bangladesh. Groundwater samples were collected from 12 Unions in November

2022, focusing on heavy metal contamination (Arsenic, Iron, Cadmium, Lead, Nickel, and Zinc) using 36 samples from various sources like submersible deep wells, houses, and mosques.

Table 1: Brief description (Sample code, Latitude and Longitude) of the sampling stations.

Sample code	Sampling points	Latitude (° N)	Longitude (° E)
S-SH-01-A	Zirani Bazar (Sina Knit & Denims Ltd)	23.99379	90.25273
S-SH-01-B	Tengguri	23.99192	90.24613
S-SH-01-C	BKSP (Dica Tex Ltd)	23.99188	90.24571
S-DH-02-A	Baipayl	23.93789	90.26998
S-DH-02-B	Unique Bus Stand (Fabriline Garments Ltd)	23.93656	90.27833
S-DH-02-C	Alia Madrasha Road (KRSS Sportswear Ltd)	23.93791	90.28046
S-PA-03-A	Puraton Para, Kurgao (S.T. Apparel)	23.90606	90.25386
S-PA-03-B	Kurgao (Siam Fashion)	23.90347	90.25206
S-PA-03-C	Kurgao Bazar	23.90641	90.25305
S-YE-04-A	Zirabo Bus Stand (Ajax Sweater Ltd)	23.91443	90.31824
S-YE-04-B	Uttar Para, Zirabo (5F Apparels Ltd)	23.91494	90.31944
S-YE-04-C	Dokkhin Para, Zirabo (PS Accessories In. Ltd)	23.91531	90.31863
S-AS-05-A	Ashulia Bazar (Maxim Label & Packaging Bangladesh Private Limited)	23.89661	90.32965
S-AS-05-B	Bangabandhu Road (Spartan Fashions Ltd)	23.89649	90.32909
S-AS-05-C	Tongabari (Tex Printing & Company)	23.89639	90.32885
S-BI-06-A	Akran Bazar (Outfit Kings Ltd)	23.85786	90.31372
S-BI-06-B	Samair (K.K. Fashion)	23.85759	90.31519
S-BI-06-C	Sadullapur Bazar	23.83103	90.32167
S-SA-07-A	Mojidpur (Global Fashion Garments)	23.84810	90.25993
S-SA-07-B	Mojidpur (Desun Garments Ltd)	23.84825	90.26009
S-SA-07-C	Rajarbari Road (Imperial Poly Products Ltd)	23.84772	90.26287
S-TE-08-A	Padma More (Padma Cans & Closure)	23.79274	90.25636
S-TE-08-B	Kathaltola (Jalalabad Steel Limited)	23.79499	90.25574
S-TE-08-C	Muchipara (Prama Group)	23.79527	90.25560
S-BO-09-A	Nikrail	23.82056	90.30196
S-BO-09-B	Bongaon	23.81687	90.30677
S-BO-09-C	Gandaria (Tanim Plastics)	23.81551	90.29131
S-AB-10-A	Amin Bazar	23.78712	90.32924
S-AB-10-B	Begun Bari	23.78829	90.32987
S-AB-10-C	Pach Gachia	23.79153	90.32855
S-KA-11-A	Naya Para (Baitul Mamur Jame Masjid)	23.79702	90.32928
S-KA-11-B	Beribadh, Singasar	23.79716	90.33099
S-KA-11-C	Kaundia Bazar	23.79816	90.33854
S-VA-12-A	South Shyampur (Manvill Style Ltd)	23.77736	90.26106
S-VA-12-B	Shyampur (Arcobaleno Footwear Limited)	23.77634	90.26128
S-VA-12-C	Haruria	23.77825	90.26129

All these samples have been analyzed for Arsenic (As), Iron (Fe), Cadmium (Cd), Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni), and Zinc (Zn). These samples were analyzed in

laboratories at the Department of Public Health Engineering (DPHE) and Dhaka International University (DIU).

In this study, a total of six physicochemical parameters were selected to assess the groundwater quality, with a specific focus on the presence of heavy metals of health and environmental concern. The selected parameters include Arsenic (As), Iron (Fe), Cadmium (Cd), Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni), and Zinc (Zn). Arsenic concentration in groundwater samples was determined using the Dual Range Arsenic Test Strip method. This method allows for the semi-quantitative detection of arsenic in two concentration ranges, typically 0–500 ppb, with colorimetric results read against a reference chart. The test was conducted under controlled laboratory conditions in the Environmental Laboratory at Dhaka International University (DIU), ensuring accuracy and repeatability. For the analysis of Iron (Fe), the FerroVer® method was employed, which is based on the formation of a violet-colored complex when iron reacts with 1,10-phenanthroline under acidic conditions. The intensity of the color, measured spectrophotometrically, is directly proportional to the iron concentration in the sample. This test was also carried out at the DIU Environmental Laboratory using standardized HACH protocols.

The concentrations of Cadmium (Cd), Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni), and Zinc (Zn) were quantified using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (Model: AAS-7000; Shimadzu), a highly sensitive and precise analytical technique suitable for heavy metal detection. These analyses were performed at the Central Laboratory of the Department of Public Health Engineering (DPHE), Mohakhali, using standard operating procedures (SOPs) to ensure data

validity and comparability. Calibration was performed using certified reference standards, and quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) protocols, including blanks and duplicates, were followed throughout the analysis. Subsequently, the analyzed results were compared to BECR-2023 (Arsenic = 0.05, Iron = 0.3-1.0, Cadmium = 0.003, Lead = 0.01, Nickel = 0.05, Zinc = 5) and WHO-2022 Standards (Arsenic = 0.01, Iron = 0.3, Cadmium = 0.003, Lead = 0.01, Nickel = 0.07).

Metal Pollution Index (MPI)

A method for evaluating the general quality of groundwater based on the quantity of different heavy metals is the Metal Pollution Index (MPI). It offers a solitary figure that represents the cumulative impact of several metal contaminants. The MPI aids in assessing the levels of pollution and any health hazards associated with metals in groundwater [10].

The pollution state of selected samples can be estimated by different indices of pollution, of which the metal pollution index (MPI) can be used as an indicator of the overall water quality related to heavy metals content, and it is calculated by the following equation[32].

$$MPI = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Ci}{MACi}$$

Where Ci is the measured concentration of each metal and MACi is the maximum admissible concentration of the *i*th metal. MPI values greater than 1 represent a threshold warning.

Table 2: Union-wise Metal Pollution Index (MPI) value.

Union Name	MPI Value
Shimulia	0.723
Dhamsona	0.886
Pathalia	0.710
Yearpur	1.04

Ashulia	0.591
Birulia	0.983
Savar	0.989
Tetuljhora	0.438
Bongaon	0.565
Amin Bazar	0.563
Kaundia	0.613
Vakurta	0.543

Health Risk Assessment

Health risk assessments typically involve sampling groundwater, analyzing it for heavy metal concentrations, and evaluating the potential health impacts based on established safety thresholds [15]. The

assessment considers factors such as the concentration of heavy metals, the duration and frequency of exposure, and the potential health effects on different populations.

Carcinogenic Risk (CR)

$$CDI = \frac{C \times IR \times EF \times ED}{BW \times AT}$$

Where:

- C = Concentration of the contaminant (mg/liter)
- IR = Water ingestion rate (liter/day)
- EF = Exposure frequency (days/year)
- ED = Exposure duration (year)
- BW = Average Body weight (kg)
- AT = Averaging time

Carcinogenic Risk,

$$CR = CDI \times SF$$

Where:

- CR = Carcinogenic Risk (unitless) (probability of developing cancer)
- CDI = Chronic Daily Intake (mg Kg⁻¹ day⁻¹) (average daily dose of a contaminant over a lifetime, considering chronic exposure)
- SF = Slope Factor (mg/kg/day)⁻¹ (risk of cancer per unit dose, specific to each contaminant)

CDI reveals the exposure dose (mg Kg⁻¹ day⁻¹) via ingestion. In this study IR_{adult} = 2.2 L Day⁻¹ and IR_{children} = 1.0 L Day⁻¹; BW is the average body weight (70.0 kg for adults and 15.0 kg for children); EF is the exposure frequency (365 days year⁻¹); ED is the exposure duration (70 years for adults and 10 years for children); and AT is the average time for non-carcinogenic (AT

(days) = ED × 365) [6]. The CR calculation result is included in Table 10.

Hazard Quotient (HQ)

The HQ is typically used to express the non-carcinogenic risk, which is computed as the ratio of CDI and RfD for specified elements by using the following equation:

$$\text{Hazard Quotient, HQ} = \frac{CDI}{RfD}$$

Where:

HQ = Hazard quotient

CDI = Chronic Daily Intake (mg/kg/day)

RfD = Reference Dose (mg/kg/day)

Table 3: RfD value of Heavy Metal with Source.

Heavy Metal	RfD (mg/kg/day)	Source
Arsenic	0.0003	US EPA IRIS
Iron	0.70	WHO,1996
Cadmium	0.005	USEPA, 1994
Lead	-	-
Nickel	0.02	USEPA, 1996
Zinc	0.30	USEPA, 1996

Table 3 displays the heavy metal toxicity responses for the RfD regarding non-carcinogenic effects. The HI value in risk assessment is calculated by adding individual HQ values. According to Molla Rahman, Masum, Ishtiaque, Sabiha, and Abul (2024), [7] elements may have non-carcinogenic impacts on human health if their respective HQ and HI values are greater than 1. The calculated result of HQ is included in Table 10.

Hazard Index (HI)

The Hazard Index (HI) is a risk assessment tool used to evaluate the potential non-carcinogenic health effects of exposure to hazardous substances, such as heavy metals. The HI is the magnitude that takes into account the joint involvement of intake, where HQ is unitless. The RfD is the reference dose of mg Kg⁻¹ day⁻¹ that originates from the risk-based concentration table. To appraise the overall potential for non-carcinogenic effects caused by multiple chemicals, the HQ intended for individual chemicals is summed and articulated as HI by using the following equation:

$$HI = \sum HQ$$

Where:

HI = Hazard Index (unitless)

HQ_i = Hazard Quotient for each contaminant i (unitless).

Chronic risk assessment is conducted by the categories like (1) Negligible Risk: where the HI or HQ is < 0.1, (2) Low Risk: where the HI or HQ is ≥ 0.1 – < 1.0, (3) Moderate Risk: where the HI or HQ are ≥ 1.0 – < 4.0 and finally (4) High Risk: where the HI or HQ is ≥ 4.0 [8]. In Table 10, the calculated result of HI is included.

**RESULTS AND DISCUSSION
Heavy Metal Concentrations in Groundwater**

The results of heavy metal concentrations in groundwater samples collected from the Savar industrial area, Bangladesh, are presented in Table 5. Some of the concentrations of heavy metals in the analyzed water samples exceeded the Bangladesh standard (BECR-2023) and the World Health Organization (WHO-2022).

Graph 1: Pearson's correlation coefficient (*r*) matrix graph among the different heavy metals.

Table 4: Chemical qualities of Groundwater and evaluation with drinking water standard.

SL No	Parameters	Measured Maximum Value	WHO, 2022 Standard	Compliance Achieved in perspective WHO	BECR, 2023 Standard	Compliance Achieved in perspective BECR
01	Arsenic (As)	0.012	0.01	Not Ok	0.05	Ok
02	Iron (Fe)	1.13	0.3	Not Ok	0.3-1.0	Not Ok
03	Cadmium (Cd)	0.0009	0.003	Ok	0.003	Ok
04	Lead (Pb)	0.011	0.01	Not Ok	0.01	Not Ok
05	Nickel (Ni)	0.05	0.07	Ok	0.05	Ok
06	Zinc (Zn)	0.05	-	-	5	Ok

Table 4 indicates whether the maximum results of the concentrations are okay or not with respect to BECR-2023 and WHO-2022, which were included in the supplementary material. The range of these heavy metal concentrations was Arsenic (0.006-0.012 mg/l), Iron (0.02-1.13 mg/l), Cadmium (0.00010-0.00090 mg/l), Lead (0.004-0.011 mg/l), Nickel (0.01-0.05

mg/l), and Zinc (0.01-0.05 mg/l). Jalalabad Steel Limited and Padma Cans and Closures Factory Limited were situated in this region, which were related to heavy metal products producing. The sample taking area selection consideration was taken logically, so that the contamination level was strategically identified.

Table 5: Chemical analysis results (Unit: mg/L)

Union Name	Sample No	Parameters					
		Arsenic (As) (mg/L)	Iron (Fe) (mg/L)	Cadmium (Cd) (mg/L)	Lead (Pb) (mg/L)	Nickel (Ni) (mg/L)	Zinc (Zn) (mg/L)
Shimulia	S-SH-01-A	0.007	0.6	0.00012	0.007	0.01	0.04
	S-SH-01-B	0.008	0.7	0.00016	0.004	0.02	0.02
	S-SH-01-C	0.009	0.5	0.00017	0.005	0.03	0.03
Dhamsona	S-DH-02-A	0.006	0.8	0.00013	0.008	0.04	0.02
	S-DH-02-B	0.010	0.6	0.00010	0.005	0.02	0.04
	S-DH-02-C	0.009	0.7	0.00090	0.005	0.03	0.02
Pathalia	S-PA-03-A	0.011	0.6	0.00016	0.007	0.02	0.03
	S-PA-03-B	0.009	0.3	0.00080	0.006	0.04	0.05
	S-PA-03-C	0.007	0.2	0.00015	0.009	0.02	0.03
Yearpur	S-YE-04-A	0.008	1.0	0.00060	0.008	0.03	0.03
	S-YE-04-B	0.007	0.9	0.00090	0.008	0.05	0.04
	S-YE-04-C	0.009	0.5	0.00012	0.007	0.03	0.02
Ashulia	S-AS-05-A	0.010	0.02	0.00016	0.010	0.03	0.03
	S-AS-05-B	0.011	0.05	0.00017	0.009	0.04	0.02
	S-AS-05-C	0.007	0.03	0.00013	0.008	0.02	0.01
Birulia	S-BI-06-A	0.012	0.9	0.00010	0.007	0.03	0.04
	S-BI-06-B	0.009	1.0	0.00090	0.008	0.02	0.02
	S-BI-06-C	0.008	0.9	0.00016	0.005	0.01	0.01
Savar	S-SA-07-A	0.006	0.6	0.00011	0.009	0.04	0.02
	S-SA-07-B	0.010	0.7	0.00014	0.006	0.02	0.03
	S-SA-07-C	0.011	1.13	0.00015	0.008	0.03	0.03

Tetuljhora	S-TE-08-A	0.008	0.09	0.00019	0.007	0.04	0.04
	S-TE-08-B	0.008	0.05	0.00015	0.011	0.03	0.03
	S-TE-08-C	0.009	0.07	0.00015	0.009	0.03	0.03
Bongaon	S-BO-09-A	0.011	0.03	0.00012	0.007	0.02	0.04
	S-BO-09-B	0.010	0.09	0.00016	0.008	0.04	0.02
	S-BO-09-C	0.008	0.06	0.00017	0.009	0.02	0.01
Amin Bazar	S-AB-10-A	0.009	0.08	0.00013	0.007	0.03	0.02
	S-AB-10-B	0.008	0.06	0.00010	0.006	0.04	0.03
	S-AB-10-C	0.009	0.03	0.00090	0.008	0.02	0.03
Kaundia	S-KA-11-A	0.007	0.07	0.00016	0.007	0.03	0.02
	S-KA-11-B	0.009	0.16	0.00015	0.010	0.03	0.03
	S-KA-11-C	0.008	0.12	0.00014	0.008	0.04	0.02
Vakurta	S-VA-12-A	0.009	0.14	0.00013	0.007	0.02	0.01
	S-VA-12-B	0.007	0.11	0.00010	0.009	0.03	0.02
	S-VA-12-C	0.010	0.09	0.00011	0.007	0.02	0.03
BECR-2023 Standard (mg/litre)		0.05	0.3-1.0	0.003	0.010	0.05	5
WHO-2022 Standard (mg/litre)		0.01	0.3	0.003	0.010	0.07	-

According to the above table, it was seen that among the 36 different parameters of the samples, the maximum value of the Arsenic samples exceeded the WHO-2022 standard. Iron and Lead slightly exceeded both the WHO-2022 and BECR-2023 standards. And rest of these parameters and

their samples were within the permissible limits of WHO and BECR.

Comparison with previous studies

The results of this investigation are consistent with those of other studies that found comparable levels of pollution in industrial areas.

Table 6: Comparison of the Heavy metal concentrations in the groundwater with other global regions and Bangladesh studies (mg/l).

SL No	Locations	As	Fe	Cd	Pb	Ni	Zn	References
1	Ethiopia		0.54-3.24	0.001-0.145	0.003-0.078	0.012-1.04	0.538-1.18	[28]
2	Mongolia	ND-0.00088		ND-0.00032	ND - 0.00009	0.00135-0.00536	0.0024-0.00979	[28]
3	India			0.00107-0.00284	ND - ND	ND - 0.03059	0.06887-0.5459	[28]
4	Iran	1.0-1.0		0.00005-0.00005	0.00217-0.00217			[37]
5	Morocco	0.00013-0.01102		0.0008-0.0042	0.00103-0.01525	0.0256-0.0761	1.0575-4.5254	[30]
6	Uganda		0.169-2.632	0.011-0.019	0.096-0.214			[31]
7	Mongolia	Nd-0.07		ND - 0.001	ND -0.06	0.01-0.07	0.003-0.13	[26]
8	Iraq		0.269	0.0031	0.0009	0.023	0.035	[38]
9	India	0.0003	0.01	0.004	0.00009		0.009	[29]
10	Bangladesh		1.67		0.049			[34]

*ND = Not Detected (Below the detection limit)

Fig. 3: Results of water test parameters of Arsenic, Iron, Cadmium, Lead, Nickel, and Zinc using the IDW interpolation method in ArcGIS 10.3.

The tested sample's value represents the concentration of the chemical parameter. This indicates the condition of that specific contaminant in the water sample. The limit of these parameters in water is different for different uses. The Environment Conservation Rules 2023 (Bangladesh), World Health Organization, European Union, US EPA, India (BIS), and other environmental organizations have set a standard limit for different parameters for drinking water. The study results are compared with the BECR 2023 and WHO 2022 limits to assess the water quality of Savar Upazila. The test results of different sample parameters are shown in Table 5. Figure 3 illustrates the concentration of Arsenic, Iron, Cadmium, Lead, Nickel, and

Zinc, using an ArcGIS map, visualizing the actual conditions of the study area in terms of concentration levels.

Using the Metal Pollution Index (MPI) and a health risk analysis based on heavy metal pollution, the groundwater quality in Savar Upazila was evaluated. The heavy metals tested included arsenic (As), iron (Fe), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), nickel (Ni), and zinc (Zn). Some metals, including lead and nickel, had moderate associations according to Pearson correlation, suggesting that they come from common sources of contamination.

The average Metal Pollution Index (MPI) value is 0.733.

Table 7: Classification and Significance of water quality based on the Meta Pollution Index (MPI).

MPI Value	Characteristics Class	Significance
<0.3	Very Pure I	It indicates negligible or no contamination by metals and also safe for human and aquatic life.
0.3-1.0	Pure II	Slight presence of metal pollutants but within acceptable limits. Considering water, soil, or sediment is still safe for most uses.
1.0-2.0	Slightly Affected III	There is little contamination, although the sources of the pollution might be found. There may be minor health and ecological concerns associated with ongoing exposure.
2.0-4.0	Moderately Affected IV	Clear signs of metal contamination. Without treatment, soil or water might not be fit for agricultural or drinking purposes. Can affect ecosystems and aquatic life if unregulated.
4.0-6.0	Seriously Affected V	significant quantities of pollutants, endangering the environment. Most often brought on by urban runoff, mining activities, or industrial discharge.
>6.0	Seriously Affected VI	Extremely high metal contamination levels, which provide serious risks to human health and the environment. Highly poisonous soil or water might have long-term negative consequences.

Elevated MPI values signify a high degree of heavy metal contamination in the surrounding environment. Such elevated heavy metal levels will adversely impact human health, with the specific effects dependent on the particular metals present and their respective concentrations.

High metal pollution liable for leading respiratory issues, such as chronic bronchitis and asthma, particularly if the metals are present in particulate matter that is inhaled[35]. Exposure to high levels of heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, arsenic, and mercury causes toxicity that result in a range of health issues, including neurological damage, kidney dysfunction, and cardiovascular problems [20].

The average MPI value was 0.733, with a range of 0.438 to 1.04. With the exception

of Yearpur Union, which displayed a higher level of contamination ("Slightly Affected III"), the majority of places were categorized as having "Pure II" water, suggesting mild contamination.

Water Quality Assessment based on MPI Values

Average MPI values revealed that none of the samples exhibited 'Pure II' quality, i.e., with a value of MPI 0.3-1.0 (Refer to MPI).

The water that was collected in Savar Upazila from the unions of Shimulia, Dhamsona, Pathalia, Ashulia, Birulia, Savar, Tetuljhora, Bongaon, Amin Bazar, Kaundia, and Vakurta was rated as "Pure II," with an MPI of 0.3 to 1.0. The only sample with a metals content classification of 'Slightly Affected III' was Yearpur, MPI 1.0-2.0.

Graph 2: Union-wise Metal Pollution Index (MPI) value.

Pearson’s Correlation Matrix (r) Analysis

Correlation coefficients are an appropriate technique that helps identify the possible source of origin of hazardous metals (Rajmohan et al., 2023). Pearson’s

correlation matrix is generally employed to illustrate the influence of studied variables on drinking water quality. The values of the coefficient (r) and their strength of correlation are categorized in Table 8.

Table 8: Interpretation of Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient (r).

Sl No.	Range of ‘r’	Interpretation
1	0.90 to 1.00	Very high positive correlation
2	0.70 to 0.89	High positive correlation
3	0.50 to 0.69	Moderate positive correlation
4	0.30 to 0.49	Low positive correlation
5	0.00 to 0.29	Negligible positive correlation or no correlation
6	-0.29 to 0.00	Negligible negative correlation or no correlation
7	-0.49 to -0.30	Low negative correlation
8	-0.69 to -0.50	Moderate negative correlation
9	-0.89 to -0.70	High negative correlation
10	-1.00 to -0.90	Very high negative correlation

Table 9: Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) matrix among the different heavy metals.

	Arsenic	Iron	Cadmium	Lead	Nickel	Zinc
Arsenic	1					
Iron	-0.04391	1				
Cadmium	-0.06206	0.495432	1			
Lead	0.154919	-0.46668	-0.27239	1		
Nickel	-0.48444	-0.17051	0.248137	0.536061	1	
Zinc	-0.39347	0.215737	0.379434	-0.26893	0.204673	1

Table 9 shows the moderate positive correlation between Pb-Ni (r = 0.536061) and the low positive correlation. Fe-Cd (r = 0.495432), Cd-Zn (r = 0.379434), negligible positive correlation, or no

correlation. Cd-Ni (r = 0.248137), Fe-Zn (r = 0.215737), Ni-Zn (r = 0.204673), As-Pb (r = 0.154919), negligible negative correlation, or no correlation. The metals As-Fe (r = -0.04391), As-Cd (r = -0.06206),

Fe-Ni ($r = -0.17051$), Pb-Zn ($r = -0.26893$), and Cd-Pb ($r = -0.27239$) all had low negative correlations. The metals As-Zn ($r = -0.39347$), Fe-Pb ($r = 0.46668$), and As-Ni ($r = 0.48444$) all had low positive correlations, which suggests they may have come from the same source of pollution. In general, elevated levels of lead and nickel in groundwater may originate from geogenic sources. The research shows that significant correlations ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) are present in Pb-Ni, Fe-Cd, Cd-Zn, As-Zn, Fe-Pb, and As-Ni. And the rest of the correlations are not statistically significant.

Pearson's correlation is used to determine the relationship between the concentrations of different heavy metals and potential sources (e.g., industrial effluents and natural background levels). Strong correlations (either positive or negative) can indicate common sources or similar behaviors of the metals in the environment. Pearson's correlation matrix can guide decisions in water quality management by showing relationships between various water quality parameters and pollution sources.

Table 10: HQ, CR & HI value for adults & children.

Heavy Metal	HQ		CR ($\times 10^{-4}$)		HI	
	Standard: HQ < 1.0		Standard: CR < 1×10^{-4}		Standard: HI < 1.0	
	Adult	Children	Adult	Children	Adult	Children
Arsenic (As)	0.920	1.940	4.130	8.750	0.997	2.116
Iron (Fe)	0.017	0.037	-	-		
Cadmium (Cd)	0.016	0.034	-	-		
Lead (Pb)	-	-	-	-		
Nickel (Ni)	0.045	0.094	8.100	17.190		
Zinc (Zn)	0.003	0.005	-	-		

The value of HQ exceeds 1 (standard: HQ < 1.0) when considering the ingestion of arsenic by children. So, the potential health effects are skin lesions, hyperpigmentation, cardiovascular diseases, neurological effects, and an increased risk of diabetes. Chronic exposure also increases the risk of skin cancer and lung cancer [24]. In this research, the HQ value depends on some factors like IR, EF, ED, BW, AT, and RfD. For long-term time exposure, ED is 70 years for adults and 10 years for children; BW is 70 kg for adults and 15 kg for children was considered in this study. If the value of BW is changed, then the risk level will be changed, especially for Arsenic and Nickel. The risk of HQ is more than twice that of adults, except for Zinc.

Since the CR value is higher than 1 in 10,000 (i.e., CR > 10^{-4}) (standard: CR < 1×10^{-4}), the risk of developing cancer over a lifetime due to exposure to the

carcinogenic contaminant is significantly higher. This increased cancer risk is particularly concerning for long-term, continuous exposure to carcinogenic substances. The health effects depend on the specific carcinogen involved and its pathway of exposure. When the carcinogenic risk (CR) value of arsenic (As) is higher than 10^{-4} (greater than 1 in 10,000), this indicates a high risk of developing cancer. Besides this, primary cancer types such as lung cancer, skin cancer, bladder cancer, kidney cancer, and liver cancer may occur. Finally, if the carcinogenic risk (CR) value of nickel (Ni) is higher than 10^{-4} (greater than 1 in 10,000), it represents a high cancer risk. In addition, lung cancer and nasal and sinus cancers are primary cancer types that may occur. Since the CR value depends on some factors like IR, EF, ED, BW, AT, and SF. For long-term time exposure, ED is 70 years for adults and 10 years for children;

BW is 70 kg for adults and 15 kg for children was considered in this study. If the value of BW is changed, then the risk level will be changed, especially for Arsenic and Nickel. CR is more than twice that of adults in terms of risk.

Our investigation revealed that the HI value is higher than 1 (standard: $HI < 1.0$). Thus, there could be a chance for non-carcinogenic health consequences. This implies a moderate risk of mild to moderate health effects, particularly for individuals like children who are sensitive or have experienced prolonged exposure. The value of HI depends on HQ, and HQ depends on some factors like IR, EF, ED, BW, AT, and RfD. For long-term time exposure, ED is 70 years for adults and 10 years for children; BW is 70 kg for adults and 15 kg for children was considered in this study. If the value of BW is changed, then the risk level will be changed, especially for Arsenic and Nickel.

Health Risk Assessment Highlighted Significant Risks

The study found that heavy metals like Fe, Cd, Zn, As, Ni, and Pb pollute the water in the Savar industrial area. The carcinogenic risk was high for arsenic and nickel, indicating an increased cancer risk. Non-carcinogenic risks (hazard quotient) were concerning, particularly for arsenic, which posed a significant risk to children. Combining all metals, the Hazard Index (HI) was above safe limits, particularly for children, signaling potential health effects. According to the findings, while groundwater quality in most areas is moderately affected, locations such as Yearpur require urgent attention. Health risks, especially from arsenic and nickel, necessitate continuous monitoring, mitigation efforts, and public health interventions to reduce exposure. Regularly testing the water quality, improving how industrial waste is managed, taking steps to protect public health, especially from

arsenic and nickel, using water filters like reverse osmosis or those with nanotechnology will help remove heavy metals. This study can help the authorities develop an appropriate plan to improve the drinking water quality, which will reduce the possibility of related health issues for the study area population. Future research should also include testing bacteria and other chemical pollutants in the drinking water.

Arsenic Test Result

The arsenic content of all groundwater samples is below the maximum permissible limit except for 03 of WHO-2022. But in perspective to BECR-2023, all the samples are below the maximum permissible limit. The concentrations of As in different locations of the study area are shown in Table 5. The highest amount, 0.012 mg/l of As, was found in Birulia union. In comparison, the lowest amount (0.006 mg/l) was found in Dhamsona and Savar (Table 5 and Graph 3). Chronic exposure to As for this value will help to pose health risks like skin lesions and increased cancer risk over time. Without mitigation, continued consumption will lead to long-term adverse health risks.

Iron Test Result

Sometimes odor and color indicate the purity of the water. The water was yellowish, or slightly yellowish, in a few study area locations, while it was odorless. The yellowish color of the water generally indicates the presence of iron (Fe) in it. Though odor is not a direct indicator of the presence of Fe in water, sometimes odorless water can contain a higher amount of Fe. The concentrations of Fe in different locations of the study area are shown in Table 5 and Graph 4. The highest amount (1.13 mg/l) of Fe was found in the Savar union. In comparison, the lowest amount, 0.02 mg/l, was found in Ashulia (Table 5). One iron water sample exceeded the permissible limit of both WHO-2022 and

BEQR-2023; the rest of the samples were within the standard limit of BEQR-2023. Taking excessive levels of Fe can cause gastrointestinal irritation and potentially affect liver function, and when not acutely toxic, high iron levels will impact water taste and bacterial growth, which will pose indirect health risks.

Cadmium Test Result

A low level of cadmium is found naturally in surface and groundwater throughout Bangladesh. In Savar Upazila, the amount of cadmium in groundwater varies. From our research, it has only been detected at a maximum level of 0.00090 mg/l of cadmium in drinking water in Birulia, Yearpur, and Dhamsona. Using and discarding cadmium-containing products can lead to higher amounts of cadmium in water. Cadmium levels may be higher in water that drains from a landfill, for instance. The majority of water samples from public drinking water systems in the research area do not have dangerous levels of cadmium. In the study area, all samples are within the standard limit, which means the groundwater is fit for drinking. It was shown in Table 5 and Graph 5. If the value exceeds the permissible limit of cadmium accumulates in the kidneys over time, long-term exposure may lead to calcium loss from bones, resulting in bone pain, sometimes helping to affect liver function, and contribute to hypertension and heart disease.

Lead Test Result

Lead is one of the heavy metals that pose enormous risks to human health and is a significant determinant of non-infectious diseases associated with toxic chemical pollution. Lead can be found in natural deposits and is commonly used in household plumbing and water service lines. Lead enters tap water through the corrosion of plumbing materials. The lead concentration limit in drinking water in the Bangladesh Standard and the WHO

Guideline is 0.01 mg/liter. From the study area, the highest amount (0.011 mg/l) of Pb was found in Tetuljhora, while the lowest amount of 0.004 mg/l was found in Shimulia (Table 5 and Graph 6). Lead exposure, even at low levels, will be harmful, especially for children, affecting cognitive function as well as neurological development. Continued exposure will lead to serious long-term health effects, including hypertension.

Nickel Test Result

Metal pipes and fittings can allow nickel to get into drinking water. When nickel seeps out of rock, it may also be found in groundwater. A rash or skin irritation may result from taking a bath in water tainted with nickel. It can cause lung function to deteriorate at low doses and cause cancer at greater doses. According to the Bangladesh Standard (BEQR): 2023, the maximum limit of Nickel in drinking water is 0.05 mg/l, and the WHO standard for Nickel in drinking water is 0.07 mg/l. From the study area, the highest amount (0.05 mg/l) of Ni was found in Yearpur, while the lowest amount of 0.01 mg/l was found in Birulia and Shimulia (Table 5 and Graph 7).

Zinc Test Result

Zinc is a naturally occurring element and can enter groundwater through various sources, including mining activities, industrial discharges, and the corrosion of galvanized pipes. Therefore, we used atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) to test for zinc in groundwater. This technique involves measuring light absorption by zinc atoms in a water sample. From the study area, the highest amount (0.05 mg/l) of Zn was found in Pathalia, while the lowest amount of 0.01 mg/l was found in Ashulia, Birulia, Bangaon, and Vakurta (Table 5 and Graph 8). All the samples were found to be within the standard limit set by BEQR-2023 and WHO-2022. Long-term high intake may lead to neurological impairments due to copper-related enzyme disruptions,

Excess zinc can interfere with the absorption of copper, potentially leading to anemia, neutropenia, and weakened

immune function as well. Chronic overexposure may disturb cholesterol levels and reduce immune response.

Graph 3: Union-wise Arsenic (As) comparison in the research area.

Graph 4: Union-wise Iron (Fe) comparison in the research area.

Graph 5: Union-wise Cadmium (Cd) comparison in the research area.

Graph 6: Union wise Lead (Pb) comparison in the research area.

Graph 7: Union-wise Nickel (Ni) comparison in the research area.

Graph 8: Union-wise Zinc (Zn) comparison in the research area.

CONCLUSION

The Savar Industrial Zone is expanding rapidly, but providing safe drinking water to its residents is a significant concern. Researchers have been analyzing the groundwater in the area to identify potential contamination with heavy metals, including arsenic, iron, and nickel. We found that one sample had too much iron. The Savar union had the worst pollution, while most other places had moderate pollution. Arsenic and nickel were the most dangerous metals with respect to carcinogenic risk (CR) for long-term drinking water with these qualities in these locations, posing risks of cancer and other health problems, especially for children. Long-term exposure to these heavy metals can damage the nervous system, heart, and development, and increase the risk of skin and lung cancer. Even though the levels of other heavy metals were safe, the overall risk was still high. This study can help the authorities develop an appropriate plan to improve the drinking water quality, which will reduce the possibility of related health issues for the study area population. Future research should also include testing bacteria and other chemical pollutants in the drinking water, as well as multiple seasonal variations. It's essential to act quickly to protect people's health and make sure the groundwater in this area is used sustainably. It is suggested to local authorities to use water filters like reverse osmosis or those with nanotechnology, which will help remove heavy metals in the research region.

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